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THE HISTORY OF THE ORIGIN OF THE INTERNET AND SITES ON IT

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Annotation: this article is written about how the internet works web pages and contacts on it.

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Nowadays, the service of the internet is becoming an excellent source of information, which is developing every day. With it, it is possible to search for data at any time in any area and copy them if it is necessary to use them. Communication on the internet in addition to the collection and publication of information, each online journalist must understand the principles and methods by which information is transmitted in what way it works. I will try to explain this using the following example. Why every minute of talking to America by phone costs 3 4 US dollars the same communication requires several 10 times less costs if done over the internet. When I study the reasons for this, it usually happens that with the help of a phone, two people have occupied this communication channel during communication, monopolizing it and the technical means involved in ensuring this communication. The longer the distance between communicating customers, the more communication tools are involved, and their cost also increases. When the Internet is done, contacts and any technical means involved in it also do not occupy a bush. Packages that arrive at the client computer are collected in a single document since each package concentrates at the same time the information about where it should be shipped and from whom one communication will be for the simultaneous transmission of packages from several customers, mixing at the same time these packages will not disappear within this stream. They are strictly controlled by special software and technical means, which clients they belong to and reach their owners in full. Thus, communication channels connecting America and Tashkent or Europe can simultaneously provide services to millions of customers. It is known that the internet is a world-wide network of hundreds of millions of computers, combining in it there are millions of specific nodes. An optional part of the network with such a complex system may be damaged or fail the node. To prevent such cases, in the network, routers are used to optimize and control the flow of packages. As a result, packages of documents transmitted from one client to another can reach several different products. It does not

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matter that the order and time of arrival at the address of the packages are different, since the package center is marked on its packages, and the special composition allows you to navigate them in the form of a single electronic document, regardless of the order in which the packages arrive. In order for the client to use the internet capabilities on the computer, it is necessary to have special software that allows you to view web pages. Such software and is called brovzer. The web brovzer MOSAICAN, which displays on the screen the very first graphic information discovered by Tim Berner, the first brovzer employee, was developed by several students. The most used vep browsers in the world are Netsappe camunication, internet explorer. One of the main requirements for web browsers is to provide full access to the web pages in the 3-period service of the internet, regardless of the technology by which the data is stored, and whether it is written in the language of the re-programs. Not all browsers can respond to this requirement. An example of this is the fact that the Visual Basis Cript language, a product of the Microsoft company, was not able to display on the screen the web pages used. And the internet extreme browser allows you to view and use the optional version without any problems.

References:

- 1.Modern internet journalism” Turayev Nurbek
2. Social Institute of journalism “ Fayzulla Muminov
- 3.Online Journalism and media” Nargiz Kasimova
- 4.Audiojournalism” Amirullo Karimov